

An Adaptive Beamforming Approach Applied to Planar Antenna Arrays Using Neural Networks

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Abstract—Future wireless networks depend on the improvement of current smart antenna operations so that they maintain high accuracy levels at low response times. Utilizing machine learning techniques, it is possible to replace the currently used algorithms with a much faster yet reliable alternative. In this study, we focus on adaptive beamforming applied to a planar antenna array using the null steering beamforming algorithm (NSB). We test different types of deep neural networks (DNNs) as potential alternative beamformers, by comparing their accuracy to that of the NSB algorithm. The application concerns an 8×8 planar antenna array composed of isotropic elements. The DNNs tested here are the traditional feedforward neural networks, the non-linear autoregressive networks with exogenous inputs, and recurrent neural networks using either gated recurrent units or long short-term memory units. In addition, we investigate each DNN type to make sure we are utilizing the best version of each neural network architecture.

Keywords—Adaptive beamforming, deep learning, gated recurrent units, long short-term memory, neural networks, non-linear autoregressive networks with exogenous inputs, null steering beamforming, planar antenna arrays, recurrent neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Current wireless networks are already facing the problem of increasing data load and network traffic. New applications and industrial innovations depend on the capacity of future wireless networks (FWNs) to support their increasing demands. To this regard, current mechanisms used for different network operations need to be upgraded. The target is to increase the number of connections a network can support without sacrificing the stability or the reliability of the connections. In this way, FWNs can achieve higher levels of throughput and higher data rates while increasing their network capacity. To overcome the existing boundaries of current technology, we need to turn to different scientific fields and introduce new approaches to known problems. Machine learning and specifically neural networks (NNs) have already proven to be a reliable and useful tool for the field of telecommunications [1]-[3]. With enough data, we can train them to be as accurate as the algorithms previously used in network operations, while taking advantage of their fast

temporal response. With this study, we attempt to find a promising NN alternative to a specific smart antenna operation called adaptive beamforming (ABF) [4], [5]. The NNs tested for this purpose are the simple feedforward neural network (FFNN), and the recurrent NN (RNN) implemented with either long short-term memory (LSTM) units or gated recurrent units (GRUs). By improving such a vital operation at the physical layer of the network, the overall response time of the network can substantially be reduced, while performance is preserved.

II. ADAPTIVE BEAMFORMING USING THE NSB ALGORITHM

Adaptive beamforming (ABF) is an important operation implemented at the physical layer of the network. It allows the antenna to dynamically steer its radiation pattern in order to maintain a stable and reliable connection with the end user. The goal is to position the main lobe of the pattern towards the direction of the desired signal while rejecting any unwanted interferences. This results in the maximization of the signal to interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR). By properly regulating the feeding weights of the elements of the antenna array, we can control the radiation pattern so that the direction of its maximum gain is facing the desired source, while making sure the pattern minima (i.e., nulls) are positioned at directions of arrival (DoAs) of interference signals. In our scenario, we consider an 8×8 planar antenna array, where each element is excited by a complex feeding number. It is assumed that each element is an omni-directional point source with distance from adjacent sources in both directions of the antenna array plane equal to $\lambda/2$, where λ is the free-space wavelength at the central operating frequency. Considering $N+1$ incoming signals reaching the antenna surface and using DoA estimation algorithms, we can identify the signal DoAs and record them using the polar angle θ and the azimuth angle φ of the spherical coordinate system. Using this information, the beamforming algorithm calculates the appropriate feeding weights to produce a proper radiation pattern. For this research, we utilize the null steering beamforming (NSB) algorithm, which provides great accuracy at the placement of the main lobe while achieving near-zero divergence at the placement of the nulls [6].

Let us consider a $P \times Q$ element planar antenna array, where P is the number of elements on the x -axis and Q is the number of elements on the y -axis (as shown in Fig. 1). If $N+1$ is the number of incoming signals, and (θ_n, φ_n) are the angles of arrival (AoAs) of the n -th signal ($n = 0, 1, \dots, N$), the theoretical steering vector for each incoming AoA is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_n, \varphi_n) = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(j\beta \vec{r}_{1,1} \cdot \vec{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \\ \exp(j\beta \vec{r}_{1,2} \cdot \vec{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \\ \vdots \\ \exp(j\beta \vec{r}_{P,Q} \cdot \vec{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where β is the propagation phase constant ($\beta = 2\pi/\lambda$), $\vec{r}_{x,y}$ is the position vector of the (x,y) array element, and $\vec{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)$ is the unit vector towards direction (θ_n, φ_n) . Based on (1), we can derive the total theoretical steering matrix \mathbf{A} :

$$\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_0, \varphi_0), \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \varphi_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_N, \varphi_N)], \quad (2)$$

which has a size of $(P \cdot Q) \times (N+1)$. Finally, the NSB algorithm calculates the desired feeding weights based on the following expression:

$$\mathbf{w}_{NSB} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{e}_1, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{e}_1 = [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T \quad (4)$$

is a unit vector of size $(N+1) \times 1$.

Fig. 1 $P \times Q$ planar antenna array.

III. DATASET PRODUCTION

For this research, we assume the simple case of 1 desired signal and 2 interference signals. Each signal is defined by its incoming AoAs. Thus, each record consists of 6 ($3 \times \theta$ and $3 \times \varphi$) AoAs within angle sectors $[0, 60]$ for θ and $[0, 360]$ for φ , with minimum angular spacing between any two adjacent incoming signals equal to 6° with respect to θ and to φ . As an output, each record contains a vector of 64 real and 64 imaginary parts of the complex feeding weights needed to feed the 64 elements of the antenna array. We also consider high noise conditions defined by a signal to noise ratio (SNR) equal to 0dB for the incoming signals. In addition, further restrictions have been applied to the records, to create the most beneficial training dataset for the NNs. Thus, we only include

cases where the maximum main lobe divergence of the radiation patterns produced by NSB is 1° and the maximum null placement divergence is 0.1° . To produce datasets, the NSB algorithm was implemented in Python using the Pytorch library [7] and the records were produced using an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 6000 GPU. The first dataset consists of 1.1×10^4 records which will be used for grid search purposes, while the second one consists of 1.1×10^6 records which will later be used to train the most promising model of each NN architecture. Both the input and output of each record are normalized in the range $[0,1]$ to facilitate the training process [8].

IV. FEEDFORWARD NEURAL NETWORK IMPLEMENTATION

The process of mapping the incoming AoAs to the appropriate weights is depicted in Fig. 2. In simple terms, AoAs are loaded in parallel at the input layer of the FFNN and are passed to hidden layers to be processed. At the output layer, we get the 128 values that represent the real and imaginary parts of the complex weights used to feed the array elements. These weights are then compared with respective weights produced by the NSB algorithm for the same AoAs using the root mean square error (RMSE) metric. The activation functions used for the hidden layers are the sigmoid function for the last hidden layer and the tangent function for all the previous hidden layers. Alternative configurations of activation functions have been tested with this one having the best training performance.

To get the best possible architecture for this 6-to-128 mapping, we perform a grid search with a 3-fold cross validation to figure out the best combination between the number of the hidden layers and their respective sizes. We use the following notation to describe all the implementations: [Size of 1st hidden layer, Size of 2nd hidden layer, ..., Size of last hidden layer]. The result of this grid search is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2 L-Layer FFNN implementation.

It seems that the most promising model is the one described with the following architecture: [128,256,512,512]. We proceed to train the final model using the bigger dataset (as described in Section III). The training results are shown in Table I.

Fig. 3 Grid search for the best FFNN architecture.

Fig. 5 GRU-RNN grid search.

TABLE I

FFNN TRAINING RESULTS

Epochs	Train RMSE	Test RMSE	Time Elapsed
81	0.035	0.036	54 mins

V. RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK IMPLEMENTATION

This approach differs from the previous implementation mostly because of the structure of its inner processing units. The RNNs in this study consist of either GRUs or LSTM units. Both provide the RNN with the ability to “remember” useful information from previous time-steps when it attempts to predict the input at the current time-step. The hidden states of each time-step processing units are passed to the next so that the final outcome, produced by the processing unit of the final time-step of the last layer, is configured based on the contribution of each input. The general process is depicted in Fig. 4, where we can see that AoAs of each incoming signal are processed by the hidden layers of the network in a sequence, at successive time-steps.

Fig. 4 L-Layer RNN implementation.

Once again, we need to investigate the possible combinations regarding the depth of the NN and the size of each hidden layer to find the most promising architecture. The results of this grid search with 3-fold cross validation are presented below. We provide results for both an LSTM and a GRU implementation.

Fig. 6 LSTM-RNN grid search.

The best architectures seem to be the 4×256 for the GRU-RNN model and 4×512 for the LSTM-RNN one. We now proceed to train the final models using the dataset of 1.1×10^6 records for each one of the above two architectures. The training results are shown in Table II. It seems that the LSTM-RNN model has reached a lower test RMSE value, while both models seem to avoid any overfitting problems. The GRU-RNN has a lower training time, indicative of its smaller size and simpler structure of its processing units. Despite the advantage it provides regarding training time, the size of this NN is also the reason behind the lower test RMSE value.

TABLE II
GRU-RNN AND LSTM-RNN TRAINING RESULTS

	Epochs	Train RMSE	Test RMSE	Time Elapsed
GRU-RNN	127	0.018	0.018	63 mins
LSTM-RNN	141	0.012	0.012	72 mins

VI. COMPARISON BETWEEN BEAMFORMERS

After we have trained the final models, we continue to perform a statistical analysis on their performance as beamformers. Each beamformer is tested using a new dataset of 10^3 records on which the NNs have no prior “experience”. The results are displayed in Table III. It seems that the SINR levels of all the proposed models are close to that of the NSB algorithm with the RNN models achieving the highest mean values. This means that all the beamformers are capable of rejecting the incoming interfering signals and keeping the desired signal clear of noise, even for the high noise conditions we have set during the dataset production (SNR=0dB). To measure the response time of each model, we measure the time each beamformer needs to produce an output for each of 10^3 records. The same GPU described in Section III has been utilized for these measurements. The results are given in Table IV.

Taking into consideration the mean SINR value, the training time and the response time of each NN model, the RNN models seem to be the most promising approach, delivering an adequate beamforming performance at a very low response time. Even though the FFNN is much faster, having both a lower training time and response time, the RNNs seem capable of achieving better beamforming performance with a potential of lowering the response time if further optimization is performed on the RNN architecture. More investigation on the accuracy of each model in terms of main lobe and null placement will be carried out as a next step of this research as well as a search for ways to decrease the size and response time of the models.

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF THE NNs WITH THE NSB ALGORITHM

Beamformer Type	SINR (dB)	
	Mean	Std
NSB	18.01	0.33
FFNN	17.38	1.36
GRU-RNN	17.81	0.82
LSTM-RNN	17.90	0.89

TABLE IV
RESPONSE TIME COMPARISON

Mean Response Time (msec)			
NSB	FFNN	GRU-RNN	LSTM-RNN
2.5	0.5	1.2	1.5

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we compare different types of NNs to investigate their potential in ABF applied to an isotropic planar antenna array. Using the NSB algorithm, we produce the dataset needed to train the NNs considering the simple case of 3 incoming signals with the first being the desired one and the latter two the interfering signals. For each NN type, we perform a grid search to find the combination of number

and size of hidden layers that gives us the best performance, and we train the final models based on that architecture. The trained models are then compared with the NSB algorithm in terms of ABF performance by observing the SINR levels achieved by each beamformer. The results shown in Section VI demonstrate that, despite their higher response time in comparison to the FFNN, the RNN models are most preferable as they reach greater SINR values. Further research on the topic is highly recommended as it appears that all NNs provide decent results and a potential for improvement.

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